

Relations between intralaminar micromechanisms and translaminar fracture behavior of unidirectional FRP supported by experimental micromechanics

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Abstract

The translaminar fracture behaviors of partially different unidirectional composite systems, constituted by the same carbon fibers but different (thermoset vs. thermoplastic) matrices, were characterized by means of compact tension fracture tests. The resulting crack resistance curves (R-curves) and fracture surfaces, were studied in detail and found to be rather different between those material systems, in spite of the same reinforcing fibers at similar volume fractions. In the attempt to justify this difference, the effects of the underlying micromechanisms were evaluated by employing experimental micromechanical measurements of the fracture characteristics of fibers, matrices and fiber/matrix interfaces. By means of a thorough analysis and quantification of the micromechanisms that contribute to the work of fracture, it was possible to decompose the translaminar fracture toughness of the composites into different contributions. Independently of the material considered, fibre bundle pull-out was found to be the mechanism that dissipates the highest amount of energy. Different patterns of bundle pull-out in different material systems were found to be the result of different outcomes from the competition of fracture micromechanisms, and to be responsible for the differences between the translaminar fracture energies of both material systems. Moreover, it was realized that the energy dissipated in bundle pull-out, hence also the overall measured translaminar fracture toughness are strongly governed by in-situ effects, i.e. effects of specimen lamination features.

Keywords: translaminar fracture, compact tension test, crack resistance (R-curve), micromechanics, fiber, matrix and fiber/matrix interface

1. Introduction

In order to optimize the use of fiber reinforced polymer composites, it is necessary to know their fracture characteristics in addition to stiffness and strength properties. Thus, the characterization of fracture behavior has been one of the most important efforts in developing composite materials for structural applications. By virtue of their hierarchical structure, the macroscale mechanical response of

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composites is manifested by the microscale mechanisms of load bearing and failure. Therefore, to better exploit the potential of these materials, their fracture behavior must be investigated in detail in order to provide understanding of the role of microscopic mechanisms on the macroscale fracture response.

The translaminar fracture toughness is one of the primary properties that requires consideration in applications where fiber breakage is the dominating failure mechanism in the composite. In fiber reinforced laminates, translaminar fracture behavior strongly depends on the microscale properties of its constituents, especially on fiber and fiber/matrix interface. In order to relate the microscale mechanisms to macroscale translaminar fracture behavior, it has been established that the energy dissipation mechanisms of fiber/matrix interface debonding and fiber pull-out contribute significantly to the fracture toughness, apart from fiber fracture [1]. Therefore, interfacial debonding and fiber pull-out have been identified as the main mechanisms for longitudinal tensile toughening [2]. It has also been concluded that the translaminar fracture toughness depends on ply thickness [3]. Recently, Pimenta and Pinho [2] proposed an analytical model based on the quasi-fractal hierarchical fracture surface of the crack propagation surface of translaminar fracture. They have shown that the translaminar fracture toughness strongly depends on fiber/matrix interface fracture energy (debonding) and friction (pull-out). In their model, they account for the effective fracture surface area as one of the key parameters attributing the fracture toughness of the composite material.

With the advent of experimental micromechanics techniques, it is possible to characterize the behaviors of the composite constituents with a high level of fidelity. The properties of the matrices and of the fiber/matrices interfaces can be measured in-situ using nanoindentation [4–6], while the fibers can be characterized by means of single-fiber tests on pristine and notched fibers [7]. Therefore, the micromechanical behaviors of the constituents can be related to the performance of the fiber reinforced material. This approach is applied in this work to investigate and understand the effects of micromechanisms on the fracture behaviour of the composite. Towards this goal, multiscale characterization is performed [8, 9]: experimental micromechanics at the constituent level, to determine the relevant mechanical properties of fibers, matrices and fiber/matrix interfaces; and experimental mesomechanics at laminate level, by means of compact tension (CT) specimens, to infer the translaminar fracture toughness of the ply. In order to put in evidence the relative effects of the relevant micromechanisms, two partially different composites are considered in this study. These are the AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 material systems which are constituted respectively by thermoplastic and thermoset matrices, but reinforced with the same carbon fibers at similar volume fractions.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the materials considered in the study and the experimental characterization of their translaminar fracture behaviors using coupon size CT specimens. The characterization of the micromechanisms is presented in section 3. The discussion of the obtained results and the proposal of relations between fracture mechanisms at micro- and meso-levels is performed in section 4. Section 5 summarizes and concludes the present work.

2. Translaminar fracture behavior

The translaminar fracture behaviors of two composite material systems have been analyzed and correlated, namely (i) unidirectional AS4 carbon fibers reinforcing the thermoset polymer 8552 and (ii) unidirectional AS4 carbon fibers reinforcing the thermoplastic polymer PEEK. The unidirectional AS4/PEEK prepreg, obtained from Cyttec [10], and unidirectional AS4/8552 prepreg, obtained from Hexcel [11], have average fiber volume fractions $V_f = 60.0\%$ and $V_f = 57.4\%$, respectively. Laminates with configuration $[0/90]_{ss}$ were prepared by hand-layup followed by pressure-temperature curing cycle as per the recommendations of the material providers [10, 11]. The thermoplastic system AS4/PEEK was consolidated by means of hot press and the thermoset system AS4/8552 has been cured in autoclave. The nominal cured ply thicknesses of AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 are 0.134 mm and 0.184 mm, respectively, resulting in the final laminate thicknesses of 4.3 mm and 5.9 mm.

2.1. Compact tension experiments

The Compact Tension (CT) test configuration, derived from the fracture characterization of metals, one of the most popular methods to measure translaminar fracture toughness of composites [1], was adopted in this work (Figure 1). To this date, many fiber reinforced materials have been characterized using the CT test approach in order to determine their longitudinal tensile fracture behaviour, as in [12–17]. Czabaj and Ratcliffe [14] listed several works with details of test specimens, crack preparation methods and data reduction methods used to retrieve crack resistance curves (R-curves) and fracture toughness values. A sharp crack tip ahead of a notch is created in the specimen by using sharp cutting tools such as a razor blade or a diamond-coated wire, among other methods. Laffan et al. [18] studied the effect of crack tip radius on CT tests of carbon fiber/epoxy composites and reported that meaningful results can be obtained with the notch radius of $250 \mu\text{m}$ or smaller.

Figure 1: Compact Tension (CT) specimen geometry and optical micrograph of sharp crack tip in specimens

Following the CT configuration proposed by Pinho et al. [13], specimens of size $65 \times 60 \text{ mm}^2$, as represented in Figure 1(a), were cut from the fabricated panels. Extending from the notch, a sharp crack of 10 mm in length was cut using a wire cutting machine, guaranteeing a crack tip radius smaller than $100 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in the micrograph in Figure 1(b). Displacement-controlled fracture tests were performed at a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min during which images have been captured in order to follow the propagation of the crack. This allowed the accurate measurement of the increasing crack length on one surface of the specimen while verifying, by visual inspection, that the crack growth occurred symmetrically on the opposite side. Nevertheless, it was not possible to verify that the crack progressed exactly with the same length in all 0° plies.

The normalized load-displacement responses of the tested CT specimens are shown in Figure 2(a). For each material system, the experimental results of five test specimens are presented. The load has been normalized by specimen thickness, since it is different between the two laminate types. It can be observed that the normalized peak load is higher for AS4/8552 than for AS4/PEEK specimens. The load-displacement responses also indicate that a stable and progressive crack propagation occurs in AS4/PEEK materials, while the crack propagation in AS4/8552 is unstable, leading to instantaneous load drops due to sudden crack extensions. The crack growth with respect to applied displacement is represented in Figure 2(b), showing faster crack propagation for the AS4/8552 material system.

Figure 2: (a) Load displacement and (b) crack progression responses of the CT specimens of AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 laminates.

2.2. Crack resistance characteristics

Different data reduction methods for CT results have been used in the literature that can be broadly grouped in two categories [19]: (i) determination of the critical stress intensity factor, K_{Ic} [16]; and (ii) Compliance Calibration (CC) method [14, 20]. Both approaches require measurement of the crack length during the fracture process, but while the first requires the anisotropic elastic properties of the laminates tested, the second approach relies on relating the compliance of the test specimen with its instantaneous

crack length. As an alternative, Catalanotti *et al.* [21] employed full field measurements using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) combined with the J-integral method to determine the R-curve.

In view of its ease of use and demonstrated accuracy [19], the CC method was adopted in this work. Hence, the compliance curves (Figure 3), $C(a) = d/P_c$, were determined from the experimental response of the specimens using the instantaneous values of the critical load to cause fracture progression (P_c), corresponding displacements (d) and crack lengths (a). The compliance with respect to crack length was described using the relation [22, 23]:

$$C(a) = C_0 + (\alpha a + \beta)^\kappa, \quad (1)$$

wherein C_0 , α , β , and κ are constants determined by least-squares fitting. It is noted that C_0 does not affect the energy release rate.

Figure 3: Compliance ($C = d/P$) of the (a) AS4/PEEK, and (b) AS4/8552 specimens obtained from experimental data.

The translamellar fracture energy of the laminate as function of crack growth, $\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^{lam}(a)$, was then determined using the Irwin-Kies relation [20]:

$$\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^{lam}(a) = \frac{P_c^2}{2t^{lam}} \frac{\partial C(a)}{\partial a} = \frac{P_c^2}{2t^{lam}} \alpha \kappa (\alpha a + \beta)^{\kappa-1}, \quad (2)$$

where t^{lam} is the specimen thickness (the remaining parameters are defined above). The crack resistance behaviour corresponding to the 0° plies ($\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0(a)$) was then obtained using the following simple rule of mixtures [3],

$$\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0(a) = \frac{\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^{lam}(a) t^{lam} - \mathcal{G}_{Ic}^{90}(a) t_T^{90}}{t_T^0}, \quad (3)$$

where t_T^0 and t_T^{90} are the summed thicknesses of the 0° and 90° plies, respectively. The fracture toughness values of the 90° plies ($\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^{90}(a)$) are relatively very low and could be considered negligible. Herein, they were taken as equal to the constant values of critical energy release rates for mode-I delamination propagation between 0° plies, as characterized previously by means of Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) tests: 1.7 kJ/m² and 0.3 kJ/m², respectively for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552.

The R-curves $\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0(a)$ for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 material systems obtained through the method just described are shown in Figure 4. For both materials, the average interpolating curves can be interpreted to increase approximately linearly from fracture initiation values up to a fracture propagation plateau. For crack lengths approaching 40 mm, the fracture energy values seem to decrease again but this a spurious effect caused by the induced compressive failure of the specimens at the back end. Hence, these values are discarded from the present analysis. From the best fitting of the data with bilinear behaviors, it is found that the average propagation fracture toughness is around 185 kJ/m² for AS4/PEEK plies and around 215 kJ/m² for AS4/8552 plies. This finding is supported by the differences in areas under the load-displacement responses (Figure 2(a)). The extrapolated crack initiation fracture toughness values are roughly 90 kJ/m² and 50 kJ/m², respectively for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 plies. The length of the fracture process zone (l_{fpz}) could also be estimated from the intersections of the two linear segments characterizing the fitted R-curve behaviors [21]. A larger fracture process zone is observed in AS4/8552 ($l_{fpz} \simeq 8$ mm) than in AS4/PEEK ($l_{fpz} \simeq 6$ mm), as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: R-curves of 0° plies of AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 laminates under compact tension tests and the length of fracture process zone (l_{fpz}) in the materials.

The most relevant characteristics of the crack resistance curves are reported in Table 1. The difference between the propagation and initiation toughness values, which can be attributed to mechanisms associated with fiber or fiber bundle pull-out [22], is roughly 95 kJ/m² for AS4/PEEK and 165 kJ/m² for AS4/8552 plies.

Table 1: Characteristics of the crack resistance curves (R-curves) obtained for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 material systems. l_{fpz} stands for the length of the fracture process zone.

Material	l_{fpz} (mm)	\mathcal{G}_{ini} (kJ/m ²)	\mathcal{G}_{prop} (kJ/m ²)	$\mathcal{G}_{prop} - \mathcal{G}_{ini}$ (kJ/m ²)
AS4/PEEK	6	90	185	95
AS4/8552	8	50	215	165

The typical fracture surfaces of the CT specimens were observed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The fracture surfaces in Figure 5 correspond to the steady state region of crack propagation. The smooth fracture surfaces of 90° plies can be clearly distinguished from the rough fracture surfaces of 0° plies. Considering the latter, it is observed that the fiber pull-out patterns in the AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 systems are significantly different. In AS4/PEEK, the pull-out mechanism occurs approximately by pyramidal fiber bundles of relatively uniform length and spacing. The pulled-out fiber bundles are observed to average approximately $400 \mu\text{m}$ in length and to have a diameter at the root ranging from 40 to $50 \mu\text{m}$ (Figures 5(a) and 5(b)). They are spaced at their tips by $175 \mu\text{m}$ at maximum, however each ply appears to accommodate two or even three pulled-out fiber bundles through-the thickness suggesting a higher average frequency. On the other hand, the fracture surfaces of the AS4/8552 plies show pulled-out fiber bundles of less uniform shape, size and frequency of occurrence (Figures 5(c) and 5(d)). On average, these structures are, however, definitely larger on AS4/8552 than in AS4/PEEK plies. The fiber bundles in AS4/8552 are measured to be as much as $1000 \mu\text{m}$ in length with a bundle width varying from $350 \mu\text{m}$ at the tip to $1000 \mu\text{m}$ at the base. Contrary to the observations in AS4/PEEK, the bundles in AS4/8552 seem to have the thickness of the whole ply, therefore showing a rectangular section at the base instead of a square/circular section for its counterpart material.

Figure 5: Fracture surfaces in the composite specimens observed under SEM.

At this point, it is evident that the nature of crack progression is inherently different between AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 systems, in spite of similar contents of the same reinforcing fibers. At the current level of observation, the indication of larger fiber bundles in AS4/8552, possibly associated with higher amounts of dissipated energy, corroborates the larger difference between initiation and propagation values of the translaminal fracture toughness of this material. The occurrence of different fracture patterns, however, is likely to be rooted in the micromechanical behavior and micro-scale mechanisms of fracture which will be analyzed in the following section. Then, the present discussion will be resumed in section 4.

3. Intralaminar failure micromechanisms

The previous analysis of the translaminal crack resistance curves and fracture surfaces reveals that there is significant difference between the two materials in study (AS/PEEK and AS4/8552), in the dissipated energies and in the fiber-bundle patterns that are generated in the fracture surfaces during the fracture process. This is likely to be attributed to the micromechanical features and properties of

150 the plies and motivates to perform characterization of the ply failure micro-mechanisms. Towards that end, in-situ micromechanical characterization has been performed in order to relate the behaviour of the constituents (fibers, matrices, fiber/matrix and fiber bundle interfaces) with the macroscale translamina failure response of the laminates. The determined properties are summarized in Table 2 whereas the testing methods are briefly introduced below.

155 3.1. Fiber elastic deformation and brittle failure

AS4 [11] fibers are high-strength carbon filaments of diameter $D = 7.2 \mu\text{m}$ manufactured from PAN (Polyacrylonitrile) precursor, and are commonly used in prepregs and dry fabrics for aerospace applications. The elastic modulus, tensile strength and fracture toughness of the fiber were determined from the quasi-static tensile tests (strain rate $\approx 10^{-3}/\text{s}$) performed on plain and notched fibers using a single-fiber 160 tensile testing equipment Textechno Favimat+ [7].

Around fifty AS4 fibers were tested to determine their average elastic modulus and plain strength distribution. The response was linear-elastic up to brittle failure with an average modulus $E_f = 229 \pm 14$ GPa. The strength data was analyzed according to Weibull statistics [24], that defines the cumulative fracture density function, F , as

$$F = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{L_f}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (4)$$

165 where σ_f is the strength of a fiber of length L_f , L_0 is a reference length which was taken equal to the test gauge length of 20 mm, σ_0 is the Weibull characteristic strength and m is the modulus of the Weibull distribution. These parameters, σ_0 and m , were computed through the least squares fitting of the experimental results for the cumulative density function of the fiber strength, obtaining $\sigma_0 = 3.959$ GPa and $m = 6.5$. Finally, from Equation 4, the average strength of AS4 fibers results in $\sigma_f = 3.687$ 170 GPa.

The fracture toughness of the fibers was determined from experiments carried out on notched AS4 fibers [7]. A sharp notch of size (a_0) to fiber diameter ratio $a_0/D \approx 0.1$ was introduced in the fiber by micro-milling using an FEI Helios NanoLab DualBeam 600i system equipped with a Focus Ion Beam (FIB), as illustrated in Figure 6(a). The notch tip radius was approximately 50 nm. The notched fiber 175 was then tested under longitudinal tension in the aforementioned Favimat+ fiber tester. The postmortem analysis of the fracture surface of AS4 fiber by SEM imaging evidenced the brittle nature of the fracture and its initiation at the notch tip, see Figure 6(b).

The mode-I fracture toughness, K_{IC} , was inferred from the residual peak stress sustained by the notched AS4 fiber (σ_∞) and the notch length (a_0) based on Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM). 180 It was assumed that the crack tip radius or the possible material modification during FIB milling operation did not significantly affect the fracture behaviour of the fiber. Under the LEFM premises, the notched fiber behaves as a linear elastic solid as far as the stress intensity of the singular field around the crack tip

(Stress Intensity Factor, SIF) remains below the fracture toughness (K_{IC}) of the material. The failure of the fiber is then dictated by

$$K_{IC}(a_0, a_0/D, \sigma_\infty) = Y(a_0/D) \sigma_\infty \sqrt{\pi a_0} \quad (5)$$

185 where $Y(a_0/D)$ is known as the non-dimensional stress intensity factor and depends on the specimen geometry and the elastic properties of the material. This parameter was determined numerically using Finite Element Analysis (FEA) for a straight fronted edge crack introduced in a cylinder under uniaxial tension [7]. By means of Irwin's relation, the fracture energy of the fibers, $\mathcal{G}_f = K_{IC}^2/E'$ with $E' = E/(1 - \nu^2)$, is found to be nearly constant with notch length with an average value of 52 J/m². More
190 details can be found in the work of Herráez et al. [7].

Figure 6: (a) Notch in the AS4 fiber for tensile test and (b) fracture surface after tensile test [7]

3.2. Matrix elasto-plastic deformation and fracture

Quasi-static nanoindentation was employed to measure in-situ the Young's moduli of the thermoplastic PEEK and 8552 epoxy matrices, by means of a Hysitron TI 950 Triboindenter equipped with a Berkovich tip. The reduced modulus was determined from the unloading response of the matrix. The Young's moduli
195 of the matrix have been determined accounting for the indenter material properties using the relation [25]

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{1 - \nu_s^2}{E_m} + \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i}, \quad (6)$$

where E and ν are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively and the suffixes m and i indicate the properties of the matrix and of the indenter tip, respectively. E_r is the reduced modulus obtained from the unloading curve. The indenter properties were taken as $E_i = 1140$ GPa and $\nu_i = 0.07$ [25]. The
200 in-situ Young's moduli of the matrices, E_m , were determined to be 4.10 GPa and 4.75 GPa for PEEK and 8552, respectively.

The tensile strength of the matrices could not be measured by in-situ tests and these data have been obtained from available data sheets [10, 11] as 100 MPa and 121 MPa, for the thermoplastic resin PEEK and for the thermoset epoxy 8552, respectively. The matrix fracture energy is also provided for the bulk
205 8552 as $\mathcal{G}_m = 90$ J/m². In the absence of better information, a similar value can be assumed for PEEK.

3.3. Fiber/matrix interface cohesive failure

The Hysitron TI 950 Triboindenter, equipped with a flat punch tip of diameter $5 \mu\text{m}$, was employed to determine the fiber/matrix interface strength by means of quasi-static push-in tests on single fibers [6]. The schematics of the fiber push-in test and the corresponding ideal load vs. indentation (or load vs. indenter displacement) response, P-h (or P-u) curve, is shown in Figure 7. The load-indentation responses obtained from the push-in tests in AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 systems are shown in Figure 7(c). Discarding the initial region in which the flat punch and the fiber are not fully in contact, the following linear response of slope S_0 is the measure of the elastic deformation of the fiber and matrix system. The interface shear strength, τ_c^{SL} , is obtained from the critical load, P_c , which represents the onset of crack propagation along the fiber/matrix interface, according to the shear lag model [26, 27]

$$\tau_c^{SL} = \frac{2nP_c}{\pi D^2}, \quad (7)$$

where n is a parameter that depends on elastic properties of fiber and matrix, and on the local fiber volume fraction, i.e. the constraint imposed by the neighbor fibers. Following the shear-lag model, n can be determined from the stiffness of the linear elastic region of the $P \rightarrow h$ curve, S_0 , according to [26, 27]

$$n = \frac{2S_0}{\pi DE_f}, \quad (8)$$

where E_f stands for the fiber longitudinal elastic modulus. However, the interface strength obtained with this methodology underestimates the actual properties, particularly in the case of composites with a large fiber volume fractions, V_f , because it does not take into account other factors such as the constraining effect imposed by the surrounding fibers, the influence of the anisotropy of carbon fibers or thermal residual stresses. To account for these factors and determine accurate values of the interface strength from push in test data in composites with $V_f > 50 \%$, Rodríguez et al. [5] developed a combined experimental-numerical approach to the analysis of fiber/matrix interface. Employing FEA of the push-in test, it was shown that the fiber/matrix interface strength was given by

$$\tau_c = A\tau_c^{SL} - B\Delta T, \quad (9)$$

where ΔT is the difference between the curing and test temperature to account for the residual stress that may arise during curing, and the fitting constants A and B are obtained by FEA. More details of this methodology can be found in [5, 6, 25].

Figure 7: (a) Schematic of fiber push in test; (b) ideal load displacement response from the push in test [5]; and (c) Response of the fiber/matrix interface obtained from push-in tests using $5 \mu\text{m}$ flat punch tip (adapted from [6]).

210 By means of this approach, the interface strengths were estimated as $\tau_c = 37 \pm 1.2 \text{ MPa}$ and $\tau_c = 64 \pm 2.6 \text{ MPa}$ for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 systems, respectively. Notice that without the corrections given by Equation 9 the interface strengths would be underpredicted by over 50% ($\tau_c^{SL} = 16 \pm 0.8$ (31 \pm 1.9) MPa for AS4/PEEK (AS4/8552)) [6].

3.4. Fiber bundle debonding

215 The debonding of fiber bundles occurs in similar conditions to mode-II transverse intralaminar fracture. Czabaj and Ratcliffe [14] have demonstrated this fracture mode to be comparable to mode-II interlaminar fracture. Hence, the fracture energy associated with fiber bundle debonding was characterized by means of the standard End Notch Flexure (ENF) test method ASTM D7905 [28] to determine the interlaminar critical energy release rate under mode-II loading (\mathcal{G}_{IIc}).

220 The ENF tests were conducted on unidirectional $[0]_{24}$ pre-cracked laminates, and \mathcal{G}_{IIc} was determined from the experimental data using beam theory [28]:

$$\mathcal{G}_{IIc} = \frac{9P_c a^2 \delta_c}{2w(L^3/4 + 3a^3)}, \quad (10)$$

225 wherein P_c and δ_c are the critical load and deflection when the crack starts to propagate, a is the initial crack length, and L and w are the length and width of the specimen. The resulting values of \mathcal{G}_{IIc} were found to be 2.09 kJ/m^2 for AS4/PEEK and 0.87 kJ/m^2 for AS4/8552. The full details of this characterization campaign are provided in [17].

Following on the idea of similarity between interlaminar and intralaminar matrix cracking, also the shear resistance to fiber bundle debonding, τ_b , can be approximated by the Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS) commonly measured by means of short beam shear tests (ASTM D2344 [29]) whose results, 94 MPa and 128 MPa respectively for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552, can be found in available material datasheets [10, 11, 30].

230

4. Correlation between intralaminar and translaminar failure mechanisms

In order to quantitatively relate failure meso-mechanisms at translaminar level and micromechanisms at intralaminar level, the fracture surfaces of AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 material systems identified in section 2 have been idealized while maintaining the relevant characteristic features, as shown in Figure 8. The differences between fracture surfaces are characterized by different bundle pull-out patterns. The SEM images of fracture surfaces revealed larger fiber bundles and longer pull out in AS4/8552, resulting in unsteady crack propagation, compared to the pulled out fiber bundles in AS4/PEEK. In the AS4/8552 ply, the pulled-out bundles are long, wide and, in most of the occurrences, are as thick as the ply. Although their dimensions are somewhat variable, for the sake of the present simplified analysis, the bundles are approximated as of uniform regular hexahedral shape with average length, thickness and width, respectively, $l_{po} = 750 \mu\text{m}$, $t_b = t_p = 184 \mu\text{m}$ and $w_b = 2 \cdot t_p = 368 \mu\text{m}$ (see Figure 8(b)). By contrast, in the AS4/PEEK plies the bundles are shorter, thinner and have a different shape. Several bundles can be observed through the thickness of the ply and they typically show a hierarchical structure by layers of decreasing number of fibers with the distance pulled-out. In the present analysis they are approximated as regular pyramidal structures of length $l_{po} = 400 \mu\text{m}$ and base width $w_b = t_b = \frac{1}{3} \cdot t_p = 45 \mu\text{m}$ (see Figure 8(a)).

Figure 8: Idealized translaminar fracture surfaces for the unidirectional composite plies analyzed.

The list of relevant fracture surface dimensions for both material systems is provided in Table 2. The micromechanical properties relevant to this analysis, which were mostly determined by means of experimental micromechanics, as described in section 3, are also summarized in Table 2. In the absence of the proper test methods, some of the required properties, however, were extracted from the literature or provided by the material manufacturers [10, 11].

Table 2: Material and geometrical micromechanical properties for AS/PEEK and AS4/8552 composites (measured or available in the literature/datasheets [6, 7, 10, 11, 30]).

Description	Symbol	Source	AS4/PEEK	AS4/8552
Fiber diameter (μm)	D	literature/datasheet	7.2	7.2
Fiber long. elastic modulus (GPa)	E_{1f}	experiments (S3.1)	229 ± 14	229 ± 14
Fiber transv. elastic modulus (GPa)	E_{2f}	literature/datasheet	12.9	12.9
Matrix elastic modulus (GPa)	E_m	experiments (S3.2)	4.10	4.75
Fibre transv. Poisson's ratio	ν_{23f}	literature/datasheet	0.46	0.46
Matrix Poisson's ratio	ν_m	literature/datasheet	0.35	0.35
Average long. fiber strength (MPa)	σ_f	experiments (S3.1)	3687	3687
Matrix tensile strength (MPa)	σ_m	literature/datasheet	100	121
Matrix coeff. thermal expansion (K^{-1})	α_m	literature/datasheet	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Fibre transv. coeff. thermal expansion (K^{-1})	α_{2f}	literature/datasheet	$7.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$7.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Curing cool-down thermal step (K)	Δ_T	datasheet/experiments	-200	-160
Fiber fracture toughness (J/m^2)	\mathcal{G}_f	experiments (S3.1)	52	52
Matrix fracture toughness (J/m^2)	\mathcal{G}_m	literature/datasheet	90	90
Bundle debonding energy (kJ/m^2)	\mathcal{G}_{IIc}	experiments (S3.4)	2.09	0.87
Fiber/matrix interf. shear strength (MPa)	τ_c	experiments (S3.3)	37	64
Bundle interf. shear strength (MPa)	τ_b	literature/datasheet	94	128
Fiber/matrix interf. friction coeff.	μ	literature	0.4-0.5	0.4-0.5
Ply thickness (μm)	t_p	datasheet	135	184
Fiber volume fraction	V_f	datasheet	0.57	0.60
Bundle debonding length (μm)	l_{deb}	experiments (S2.3)	800	1500
Bundle pull-out length (μm)	l_{po}	experiments (S2.3)	400	750

Some authors, e.g. Kelly [31], Kim and Mai [32], have analyzed longitudinal fracture of fiber-reinforced materials by considering failure micromechanisms such as debonding, fracture and pull-out of individual fibers. In composites with relatively high fiber volume fractions, these mechanisms likely occur at the level of hierarchical fiber bundles, as previously described by Pimenta and Pinho [2, 33] and observed in section 2.3. Both cases translate the effect of splitting, either at fiber/matrix level or at intraply level. The mechanism of longitudinal splitting of individual fibers was first identified by Cook and Gordon [34] and is explained as follows by Greenhalgh [35]. A tensile stress exists ahead of the crack tip of a tensile crack growing transverse to fibres in a unidirectionally reinforced ply. In addition, an associated shear stress develops to provide stress equilibrium since there is no stress across the crack faces. When this crack approaches an intact fiber, the shear stress leads to fiber/matrix interface shearing that will ultimately induce debonding of the fibers. Moreover, this mechanisms acts to blunt the crack, and may

inhibit further crack growth perpendicular to the fibers.

In the previous explanation, it is assumed that fiber breaks occur independently of one another, that is
265 to say that the failure of a fiber does not immediately lead to failure of its neighbor at the same ply cross
section. Nevertheless, the competition between splitting and fiber fracture mechanisms is dominated by
the relation between strengths of fiber and fiber/matrix interface. If the fiber/matrix interface strength
is relatively high, the degree of fiber debonding is limited before the occurrence of fiber failure, and the
crack propagates across the fibers. This leads to a relatively smooth fracture surface, often referred to
270 as brittle fracture. However, if the fiber/matrix interface strength is relatively weak, the degree of fiber
debonding is extensive before fiber failure occurs and a 'broom-like' failure surface of pulled-out fibers
may result, as explained by Greenhalgh [35]. A criterion suggested by Kelly [31] to evaluate if fiber
breaks occur independently of one another is $\tau_c \ll \sigma_f \sqrt{G_m/E_f}$. This condition expresses that the shear
strain energy stored elastically in the matrix at failure of the interface should be much lower than the
275 strain energy stored in a fiber prior to failure [31]. Applied to the present cases of similar fiber volume
fractions, this criterion yields relations of 1:8.2 and 1:5.1, for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552, respectively,
which are not particularly low, although significantly lower for AS4/PEEK. Moreover, this difference is
almost entirely due to the different values of τ_c since the fibers are the same in both material systems
and the matrices have similar elastic properties, as demonstrated in section 3.

280 'Broom-like' failures are typical of composites with relatively low fiber volume fractions. For advanced
unidirectional CFRP which typically have high V_f associated with dense fiber packings, debonding and
pull-out usually occur at the level of fiber bundles, as represented in Figure 8 in simplified form. These
formations lead to longer pull-out distances which are counteracted by narrower debonding and pull-
out surfaces. According to experimental observations [13, 36], fracture propagates inwards the ply and
285 downwards in the hierarchical structure of the broken bundle composed of hierarchical levels of decreasing
number of fibers. In cross-ply CT specimens, failure of the 0° ply initiates at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces and
propagates inwards [2, 36]. However, the cases analyzed in this work suggest that there is an alternate way
for this failure process (see Figure 8). Whilst the process described by [2] is observed in the AS4/PEEK
cross-ply laminates, in the CT samples of AS4/8552 material, the failure initiated at $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces
290 does not seem to readily propagate inwards the 0° ply. Instead, the cracks propagate in shear mode along
the interface for some critical distance. Together with split cracks that propagate through the ply with
some periodicity, bundles of approximated hexahedral shape are formed that finally break in a brittle
manner. The reason for these different behaviors can again be construed around the properties of ply/ply
and fiber/matrix interfaces. As shown by experimental evidence reported in section 3, the fiber/matrix
295 interface shear strength (τ_c) of AS4/8552 is much higher than that of AS4/PEEK (Table 2). This inhibits
fiber/matrix debonding and the appearance of hierarchical-level bundles in the AS4/8552. But instead
of this being an indication that a brittle failure mode would occur, the crack propagates first through
a third element in the cross-ply laminate, i.e. the ply interface. Moreover, according to experimental
ENF measurements reported in section 3, the shear mode fracture energy (\mathcal{G}_{IIc}) for AS4/8552 interfaces

300 is much lower than that of AS4/PEEK interfaces (Table 2), indicating that fiber/matrix debonding is likely to be favored by ply-interface in AS4/PEEK.

When an individual fiber debonds from the matrix, it can be assumed that the work done in the debonding process appears as strain energy in the fiber, so the maximum value of this work of fracture occurs when the stress in the fiber reaches its breaking strength, σ_f , which occurs at a critical debonding
305 length [31]

$$l_c = \frac{D \cdot \sigma_f}{4 \cdot \tau_c} \quad (11)$$

An equivalent expression can be derived for the debonding and breakage of fiber bundles of strength σ_b ,

$$\frac{l_{deb}}{2} = \frac{C_b \cdot \sigma_b}{P_b \cdot \tau_b} \quad (12)$$

wherein σ_b is the bundle strength, C_b is the maximum section of the bundle and P_b the average section perimeter. Assuming, for simplicity, the idealized fracture surfaces represented in Figure 8, that the bundle strength can be deterministically approximated by $\sigma_b = V_f \cdot \sigma_f$, values of $l_{deb}/2 = 0.53$ mm
310 and $l_{deb}/2 = 1.01$ mm are found for AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 bundles, respectively. These results are relatively close estimations of the average experimental measurements (Figure 5).

In order to correlate micromechanisms with the fracture toughness of the fiber reinforced composites, several theories have been proposed to explain the contributions of the constituents to the work of fracture. Among several mechanisms, interface debonding, pull-out friction, matrix shear flow, fiber stress
315 redistribution are often considered as predominant mechanisms that contribute to the work of fracture, as proposed by Kim and Mai [32]. Recently, Pimenta and Pinho [2] developed a model to predict translam- inar fracture toughness based on hierarchical fracture surface of pulled out fiber bundles accounting for fiber matrix interface properties and friction during pull out. Their model [2] suggests that at the con- ventional ply scale ($t_{ply} \approx 0.125$ mm), pull-out and debonding have similar contributions. However, the
320 size of the pull-out bundles has significant effects as well: debonding dominates for small bundles, but pull-out becomes increasingly important for larger bundles. In addition to that, the interfacial toughness has a complex effect on the fracture toughness.

The contribution of the micromechanical mechanisms to the translam- inar fracture toughness can be estimated on the basis of the fracture surface characteristics and micromechanical properties analyzed
325 above and reported in Table 2. Herewith, four micromechanical mechanisms are considered to significantly contribute to the work of fracture of the composite, namely, (i) breakage of fibers (ii) damage and failure of matrix (iii) debonding of the bundles, (iv) pull-out of the bundles. In the present analysis, the contribution of the plastic deformation of matrix is included in the terms associated with matrix damage and bundle debonding, in contrast with other authors that consider these contributions separately [32, 37].

- **Fiber breakage:** The contribution of the work of fiber breakage to the failure of the fiber bundle can be determined from the size, volume fraction and experimentally measured toughness of the

fibers, in the following way

$$R_{fb} = \mathcal{G}_f \cdot V_f \cdot C_b, \quad (13)$$

330 wherein \mathcal{G}_f is the fracture toughness of the fibers, V_f is the fiber volume fraction in the composite, and C_b is the cross-sectional area of the bundle.

- **Matrix damage and failure:** The work of matrix damage and cracking can be determined in a similar way, given by

$$R_{mdc} = \mathcal{G}_m \cdot (1 - V_f) \cdot C_b, \quad (14)$$

wherein \mathcal{G}_m is the fracture toughness of the matrix. This contribution accounts only for the matrix fractured in opening mode, i.e. due to the stresses normal to the projected section of the bundle. The contribution of the resin fractured in shear mode is taken into account in the work associated with the debonding of the fiber bundle.

335

- **Bundle debonding:** The work of fracture associated to the debonding of fiber bundles is given by [32]:

$$R_{deb} = \mathcal{G}_{IIc} \cdot A_{deb}, \quad (15)$$

wherein A_{deb} is the fully debonded surface of the bundle. For the type of fracture surface identified in the AS4/8552 plies, idealized by regular hexahedral bundles, $A_{deb} = 4 \cdot \frac{l_{deb}}{2} \cdot t_p$, as shown in 8(b). For AS4/PEEK plies, whose fracture surface can be idealized by regular pyramidal shapes, $A_{deb} = 2 \frac{t_p}{3} \sqrt{\left(\frac{t_p}{6}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{l_{deb}}{2}\right)^2}$, as shown in 8(a).

- **Bundle pull-out:** The work of post-debonding frictional stresses that develop on the fiber bundle surface during pull-out is given, in general form, by

$$R_{po} = A_{po} \cdot \tau_\mu \cdot l_{po}, \quad (16)$$

340

where the frictional stresses, assumed constant over the pull-out length, l_{po} , can be estimated by $\tau_\mu = \langle -\sigma_n \rangle \cdot \mu$ where $\langle -\sigma_n \rangle$ is the compressive stress ($\langle x \rangle = \max(0, x)$) on the fibre bundle surface, and μ is the friction coefficient. There are, however, several sources of frictional stresses acting on the bundle faces during pull-out.

At micromechanical level, compressive stresses on the debonded fibre/matrix interfaces, σ_R^{micro} , develop because of the micro-residual thermal stresses generated during the curing cool-down step, ΔT , due to the mismatch between the thermal expansion coefficients of the composite constituents in the plane transverse to the fibres (α_m for matrix and α_{2f} for fibres)[31, 32]. The micro-residual stresses applied on a fibre bundle can be calculated by

$$\sigma_R^{micro} = C_S \cdot p \quad (17)$$

wherein C_S is a micro-to-meso surface factor defined as

$$C_S = \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{3}\pi V_f}{2}} \quad (18)$$

for hexagonal fibre packings. The residual pressure on single fibres in a multifibre reinforced ply, p , is defined by Pimenta and Pinho [2] as

$$p = \frac{(-\epsilon_m^{\Delta T} + \epsilon_f^{\Delta T}) \cdot E_{2f} \cdot E_m \cdot (1 - V_f)}{E_{2f} \cdot (1 - \nu_m) + E_m \cdot (1 - \nu_{23f}) + V_f \cdot [E_{2f} \cdot (1 - \nu_m) - E_m \cdot (1 - \nu_{23f})]} \quad (19)$$

where $\epsilon_m^{\Delta T} = \alpha_m \cdot \Delta T$ and $\epsilon_f^{\Delta T} = \alpha_f \cdot \Delta T$ are the stress-free deformations induced during curing cool-down on the matrix and fibres, respectively. Moreover, E_m and ν_m are the matrix elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio, and E_{2f} and ν_{23f} are the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the fibres in the transversely isotropic plane (see Table 2).

Due to the laminated configuration of the CT test specimens, macro-residual stresses also develop due to the orthotropic elastic and thermal expansion behaviors of the plies. These lamination residual stresses, acting exclusively in the plane of the laminate, are superimposed to the micro-residual stresses and are bound to influence the bundle pull-out behaviour. The macro-residual stresses in the laminated coupons of both materials can be calculated by means of Classical Lamination Theory (CLT), as presented in [38], using the homogenized ply properties available in [10, 11, 30]. To meet the condition of zero through-thickness stress resultants in the cross-ply CT laminated specimen, it results that compressive stresses are generated along the longitudinal ply directions which are in equilibrium with transverse tensile stresses of equal magnitude. The later ones, σ_R^{meso} , are relevant for the fibre bundle pull-out mechanism in spite of having the effect of counteracting bundle constraining in the ply plane.

Poisson effects constitute another source of stresses normal to the debonded fibre bundle faces. Ply transverse and out-of-plane ply contractions arise due to longitudinal tensile loading, considered stress-free in the homogeneous ply under the elastic regime. When fibre bundles are broken and debonded they unload longitudinally and are freed of Poisson's transverse contraction. The deformation mismatch between the unloaded fibre bundle and the surrounding laminated plies generates constraining stresses on the faces of the bundles whose magnitude can be estimated by $\sigma_{\nu Constrain} = -E_2 \cdot \nu_{12} / E_1 \cdot X_T$, where E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} and X_T are homogenized ply properties; longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli, Poisson's ratio for the fibre planes and longitudinal tensile strength, respectively [10, 11, 30].

The three different types of stresses acting transversely to the fibre bundle faces are schematically represented in Figure 9. Their intensities are given in Table 3 for both material systems. It is striking that the magnitude of the macro-residual stresses is 4-5 times higher than that of the micro-residual stresses. Hence, it can be concluded that the pull-out behaviour obtained from the CT tests is severely influenced the laminate configuration. Another interesting observation is that the resulting constraining stresses, σ_n^f , on the bundle faces normal to direction 2 (in-plane transverse; faces 1 and 3) are much lower than the ones normal to direction 3 (out-of-plane; faces 2 and 4) due to the stress relief effect caused by the tensile macro-residual stresses.

Figure 9: Schematic representation of constraining stresses on fibre bundle surfaces during pull-out.

Table 3: Normal stresses acting on the fibre bundle faces during pull-out.

	Face Nr. (f)	σ_R^{micro} [MPa]	σ_R^{meso} [MPa]	$\sigma_{VConstrain}$ [MPa]	σ_n^f [MPa]
AS4/PEEK (dir. 2)	1, 3	-8.8	39.0	-49.4	-19.2
AS4/PEEK (dir. 3)	2, 4	-8.8	-	-49.4	-58.2
AS4/8552 (dir. 2)	1, 3	-10.0	47.0	-49.1	-12.1
AS4/8552 (dir. 3)	2, 4	-10.0	-	-49.1	-59.1

Given the different frictional stresses on different surfaces of the fibre bundles, Equation 20 is reformulated as

$$R_{po} = l_{po} \cdot \mu \cdot \sum_1^{f=4} (A_{po}^f \cdot \langle -\sigma_n^f \rangle) \quad (20)$$

The friction coefficient, μ , is assumed to be constant but is not known exactly. As a reference, a previous parametric micromechanics study conducted by the authors concluded that the coefficient of friction of the fiber/matrix interface in AS4/8552 plies should be at least 0.4 [25]. A close value can be assumed for the whole fibre bundle surfaces in both material systems.

To obtain the strain energy release rate contributions of each of these mechanisms to the fracture of the bundle, which can be considered equal to that of the ply, the work of fracture is divided by the area of the bundle projected onto the ply fracture surface, C_b , with $C_b = t_p^2$ for AS4/8552 and $C_b = \left(\frac{t_p}{3}\right)^2$ for AS4/PEEK. Hence, the translaminal fracture toughness of the ply can be estimated with this method by

$$\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0 = \frac{R_{fb} + R_{mdc} + R_{deb} + R_{po}}{C_b}, \quad (21)$$

380 Estimations of the contributions of different mechanism to the total translaminal fracture energy of the two different composites studied in this work are presented in Table 4. In the lack of an objective value

for the coefficient of fiber bundle surface friction, different estimations are presented for two scenarios, $\mu = 0.4$ and $\mu = 0.5$. In so doing, the resulting ranges of estimations for \mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0 closely match the values measured by means of CT tests (see section 2). Moreover, in accordance with the experiments, the decomposition of micro-mechanisms also reveals that the work of fibre bundle pull-out has, by far, the largest contribution to the translamina fracture energies of both material systems.

Table 4: Translamina fracture toughness (\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0) of AS4/PEEK and AS4/8552 plies estimated from the contributions of energy dissipation micro-mechanisms to the work of fracture.

	\mathcal{G}_{fb} [kJ/m ²]	\mathcal{G}_{mdc} [kJ/m ²]	\mathcal{G}_{deb} [kJ/m ²]	$\mathcal{G}_{po} (\mu=0.4)$ [kJ/m ²]	$\mathcal{G}_{po} (\mu=0.5)$ [kJ/m ²]	$\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0 (\mu=0.4)$ [kJ/m ²]	$\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0 (\mu=0.5)$ [kJ/m ²]
AS4/PEEK	0.031	0.18	37.2	110.2	137.8	147.5	175.1
AS4/8552	0.030	0.05	10.6	144.7	217.9	185.0	228.6

The analysis of the different fracture micromechanisms shows that, as expected, the contributions to translamina fracture of fiber breakage and net matrix cracking are very small as compared with bundle debonding and pull-out. Among these last two mechanisms, bundle pull-out is the most dissipative in both material systems, although it is estimated to be less pronounced in AS4/PEEK than in AS4/8552. This is because this mechanism is largely controlled by the bundle pull-out surface which is significantly larger in the latter material system. Counteracting, although not overcoming this tendency, the work of bundle debonding is more significant for AS4/PEEK than for AS4/8552 due to the higher bundle debonding energy of the former. These findings correlate qualitatively well with the characteristics of the R-curves obtained in section 2 that reveal a stronger contribution of fiber bundle pull-out mechanisms to the translamina fracture in the AS4/8552 system.

Remarkably, the largest contributions to fibre bundle pull-out and to the overall translamina fracture energy measured in CT tests seem to be macro-residual stresses and Poisson effects, both of which are related to specimen lamination. If both effects are discounted from the fracture energy contributions, the estimated bundle pull-out energies, assuming $\mu=0.5$, would come as $\mathcal{G}_{po} = 31.2$ (61.2) kJ/m² for AS4/PEEK (AS4/8552). The total translamina fracture energy would result as $\mathcal{G}_{Ic}^0 = 68.5$ (71.9) kJ/m² for AS4/PEEK (AS4/8552). These estimations cannot be attributed directly to the isolated ply since they are based on the fibre-bundle geometric features which are also dependent on specimen lamination, as discussed above. Nevertheless they are probably closer to intrinsic ply properties than the values determined through CT tests.

5. Conclusions

This work explored the relationship between intralaminar fracture micromechanisms and translamina fracture behavior of advanced unidirectional composites for aeronautical applications. To this purpose,

two CFRP systems have been considered, having the same fibers (AS4) at similar volume fractions, but
410 different matrices (the thermoplastic PEEK vs. the thermoset 8552 epoxy). The translaminar fracture
behaviors of these systems were characterized using the Compact Tension test method in combination
with the Compliance Calibration approach and SEM observation of the fracture surfaces. The two
material systems were shown to have clearly distinguishable fracture propagation features: the extracted
R-curves showed different characteristics and the fracture surfaces revealed distinguishable fiber bundle
415 pull-out patterns.

To elucidate such different behaviors, the underlying fracture micromechanisms were analyzed in de-
tail with quantification of the relevant micromechanical properties, when possible. This involved the ex-
perimental micromechanical characterization of the individual fibers, matrices and fiber/matrix interfaces.
With this information and the relevant features of the fracture surfaces, it was possible to decompose the
420 total work of translaminar fracture into the contributions of four main fracture micromechanisms (fiber
breakage, matrix damage, fiber bundle debonding and fiber bundle pull-out) and explain the difference in
R-curve behaviors between both material systems. It was also possible to justify the different translami-
nar fracture patterns as the result of different outcomes from the competition of fracture micromechanisms
in each material. It was concluded that fiber bundle pull-out dissipates, by far, the highest amount of
425 energy. This mechanism is largely controlled by the bundle pull-out surface which is significantly larger in
AS4/8552 as compared to AS4/PEEK. This is judged to be mostly due to the lower mode-II interlaminar
(and transverse intralaminar) cracking energy release rate that leads to the favoring of the corresponding
fracture modes in the former material system, and the build-up of larger fiber bundle structures before
they fail by fiber breakage. Remarkably, it was realized that the frictional energy dissipation during
430 bundle pull-out is strongly governed by in-situ effects, i.e. effects of specimen lamination features such
as macro-residual stresses and Poisson effects. Therefore, the translaminar fracture toughness measured
through CT tests cannot be considered a characteristic of the ply alone. The contribution to translami-
nar fracture of fiber bundle debonding is also significant, however the works of fiber fracture and matrix
cracking can be considered negligible in comparison with the remaining micromechanisms.

435 The understanding of these micro- and meso-scale mechanisms and effects gives helpful insight towards
the design of composites with optimized fracture toughness.

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